

“ENHANCING STUDENTS READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH THE JIGSAW COOPERATIVE LEARNING MODEL AT JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL”

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine how effective the jigsaw cooperative learning model is in improving junior high school students' ability to read and understand English texts. This article was written using a literature review by analyzing several studies related to the topic of discussion, namely: cooperative learning, the jigsaw learning model, reading skills, and the context of English language learning in junior high schools. According to the literature, cooperative learning is learning in a small heterogeneous group to work together, train students to exchange thoughts, ideas, and opinions, and solve problems with shared responsibility and goals, as well as positive interdependence and collaboration. The jigsaw cooperative learning model specifically emphasizes the formation of groups consisting of heterogeneous original groups and then forming expert groups to make students responsible for an assigned topic and then sharing information with friends who discuss different topics in their original groups. Previous studies, such as Herlina et al. (2019), Dinar et al. (2021), Muhaenah (2023), and Suharti (2017), found that the jigsaw type can increase student motivation or learning activities and reading comprehension by facilitating more intense discussions, more focused information sharing, and peer learning processes, which make them more active and confident in understanding the text content. Based on a review of research results on jigsaw-type cooperative learning, it was found that collaborative learning such as jigsaw can affect students' achievement and learning outcomes in English in reading or text comprehension. It was also proven that jigsaw-type cooperative learning can improve the ability and understanding in processing information. Overall, jigsaw-type cooperative learning can be an effective alternative for teachers to improve junior high school students' English text comprehension skills.

Keywords: *cooperative learning, jigsaw, reading comprehension, English, junior high school students, collaborative learning*

INTRODUCTION

Education at the junior high school level plays an important role in fostering students' academic abilities, including literacy. One important aspect of literacy is students' ability to understand and process information. According to Tampubolon in (Jahrir, 2020), reading is one of the four basic language skills and is part of written communication. Reading is a process of skill development, starting from the ability to understand words, sentences, and paragraphs in

a text to critically and evaluatively comprehend the entire content of the text. Meanwhile, according to Dalman in (Astutik, Desy and Kuntarto, Eko and Hayati, & Suci, 2021), reading is a cognitive process carried out to obtain various information and insights contained in a piece of writing. It can be concluded that reading ability is a person's ability to pronounce, spell, recite, and understand critically and evaluatively the entire content of the reading material.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Based on Permendiknas Nomor 22 Tahun 2006 tentang Standar Isi dan Permendiknas Nomor 23 Tahun 2006 tentang Standar Kompetensi Lulusan, English is one of the compulsory local subjects for all elementary school students from grades I to VI. The inclusion of English as a compulsory subject indicates that foreign language skills, including reading, are considered a basic competency that must be mastered from an early stage of education. When entering junior high school, the demands on English text comprehension become increasingly complex because students are expected to achieve literacy competence by understanding various types of texts. However, in practice, many students still experience difficulties in understanding English texts, either due to limited vocabulary, lack of reading strategies, or low motivation to learn. Therefore, this study aims to find an effective learning model to help students understand English texts and overcome the obstacles they encounter in the reading process. One alternative that can be applied is the cooperative learning model, as this model emphasizes cooperation among students, active interaction, and structured information exchange.

METHOD

This article uses a literature review method by analyzing various relevant sources on cooperative learning models and their implementation in the context of English language learning in junior high schools. As explained by Muktiadji and Kamil (2021), a literature review is a systematic research method to identify, evaluate, and integrate findings from previous studies on a particular topic. The reference sources discussed in this study are taken from books, journal articles, proceedings, and others. This literature review aims to review various cooperative learning models, including the Jigsaw model, in the context of English language learning in junior high schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cooperative Learning

Wagitan (2006) concluded that active learning, including cooperative learning, can improve learning effectiveness. Using cooperative learning can change the role of teachers from teacher-centered to managing students in small groups. Cooperative learning models can be used to teach complex material and can help teachers achieve learning objectives that are social and interpersonal in nature. According to Slavin in Laboron (2010), cooperative learning is defined as follows “*cooperative learning methods share the ideas that students work together to learn and are responsible for their teammates' learning as well as their own.*” This definition implies that in cooperative learning, students learn together, contribute their thoughts, and are responsible for their individual and group learning outcomes. This group learning process can train students to exchange thoughts, ideas, and opinions.

Jigsaw Cooperative Learning

The jigsaw cooperative model is a form of cooperative learning that is widely used to improve students' understanding of texts. This model places students as “experts” in certain parts of the text, then they share their knowledge with their initial group, so that the reading process becomes more collaborative and meaningful. According to Isjoni (2009), jigsaw cooperative learning is a type of cooperative learning that encourages students to be active and help each other in mastering the subject matter to achieve success. Lie (2004) states that jigsaw is designed to increase students' sense of responsibility for their own learning and also for the learning of others. Students not only learn the material provided, but they must also be prepared to share and teach the material to other members of their group. Thus, students are dependent on one another and must work together cooperatively to learn the assigned material.

According to Elliot Aronson, the implementation of jigsaw classes consists of 10 stages, namely:

1. Divide students into jigsaw groups of 5–6 people;
2. Assign one student from each group as the leader, generally the most mature student in the group;
3. Divide the lesson to be discussed into 5–6 segments;
4. Assign each student to study one segment and master their own segment;

5. Give students the opportunity to quickly read their segment at least twice so that they become familiar with it and do not have time to memorize it;
6. Form expert groups with one person from each jigsaw group joining other students who have the same segment to discuss the main points of their segment and practice presenting to their jigsaw group;
7. Each student from the expert group returns to their jigsaw group;
8. Ask each student to present the segment they have studied to their group, and give other students the opportunity to ask questions;
9. The teacher goes around from one group to another, observing the process. If any student disrupts the process, the assigned group leader immediately intervenes appropriately;
10. At the end of the section, give a test on the material so that students know that this section is not just a game but actual reading.

From the above description, the steps of cooperative learning using the jigsaw technique can be described in the following:

Formation of jigsaw type cooperative groups:

Home Teams (5 or 6 members grouped heterogeneously):

(Each expert teams has 1 member from each of the home teams)

Formation of Jigsaw Cooperatives (adopted from Arends, 1997)

According to Sharan (2012), jigsaw is a structure that can be used for cooperative problem solving. The following is a guide for problem solving using jigsaw:

1. Division of tasks: Tasks or sections of text or problems are divided into several components (or themes).
2. Core groups: Each group member is assigned a theme so that they can become an expert on it.

3. Expert groups: Students who have been assigned the same theme gather in expert groups to discuss the theme, master it, and plan how to teach it.
4. Core group: Students return to their original groups and share what they have learned with their group members.

The jigsaw model effectively improves students' reading skills, as long texts are broken down into smaller sections. Students do not feel overwhelmed by the content of the reading as a whole because this division of the text allows them to concentrate on one subtopic thoroughly. In addition, it can make the reading process more meaningful because students read for themselves and to teach their friends. The 2013 curriculum stipulates that teachers must apply learning methods that encourage student activity and improve their thinking skills (Maro, 2016). This is in line with the cooperative learning model, which emphasizes cooperation, discussion, and active participation in understanding the material, including English reading texts. Therefore, cooperative learning, such as the jigsaw method, can be a relevant method to help students understand texts more deeply through interaction and division of learning tasks.

The Use of Jigsaw Cooperative Learning in Understanding English Texts in Junior High Schools

Teaching English text comprehension in junior high school requires the application of appropriate learning models in order to improve students' reading and comprehension skills. One such model is jigsaw cooperative learning. There has been much research conducted on jigsaw cooperative learning in English text comprehension.

As shown in the research by Herlina, Romdanih, and Harmayanthi (2019), there is a significant effect on the application of the jigsaw cooperative learning model on the learning outcomes of narrative text comprehension by students at SMPN 2 Cikarang Barat. The results of research by Dinar, Sunarmo, and Yunaika (2021) also show that the implementation of the jigsaw cooperative learning model has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of students at SMPN 18 Tangerang. In addition, the results of Muhaenah's (2023) research show that jigsaw cooperative learning improves the learning outcomes of students at SMPN 1 Mallusetasi because students feel more excited and happy working in groups. This shows that the application of jigsaw cooperative learning has a positive impact on English learning. As shown by the results of Suharti's (2017) research, which revealed that jigsaw cooperative learning can improve the understanding of students at SMPN 28 Purworejo of narrative texts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of the Jigsaw learning model in the context of English language learning at the junior high school level is carried out through three main stages, namely initial activities, core activities, and final activities. The following is an explanation of the steps:

“Implementation of Jigsaw Groups for Exploring Elements of Narrative Text”

<i>Pre-activity</i> (Initial activities)
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The teacher explains the learning objectives.2. The teacher provides a brief overview of the topic to be discussed.3. The teacher motivates students to prepare themselves and focus on the topic.4. The teacher asks simple questions to stimulate students' curiosity before moving on to the main material.
<i>Main-activity</i> (Core activities)
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Students are given an explanation of the English text topic to be studied, accompanied by examples of comprehension questions and discussions. For example, students study narrative texts; then divide students into several groups that focus on elements within Narrative Texts such as Characters, Setting, Plot, Conflict, and Resolution.2. Students are divided into heterogeneous groups based on academic ability, learning interests, and individual characteristics such as gender or learning style. Each group consists of 5-6 students. Next, each student in the original group is assigned a number such as 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5. Numbering is done randomly, for example by distributing small numbered pieces of paper that are rolled up, then each student is asked to take one roll. This number determines the part of the text that each student will study. These groups are called <i>Home teams</i>.3. Based on the numbers obtained by students from their home teams, students with the same numbers then gather to form new groups called <i>Expert teams</i>.4. Students discuss in expert groups according to the given discussion topics. The teacher guides and directs students to actively participate in the discussion and assists them if they have questions or encounter difficulties.

5. After finishing the discussion in the expert groups, the students return to their original groups (*home teams*). At this stage, each student is responsible for explaining the section of the text that they studied in the expert group to their teammates. The teacher guides the groups as they work and learn.

Post-activity
(Final activities)

1. Each group presents their work to gain a comprehensive understanding and complement each other's knowledge.
2. The teacher gives other students the opportunity to ask questions.
3. The teacher praises the best group and gives guidance to the other groups, finding ways to appreciate both the test and individual/group results.
4. The teacher evaluates and summarizes the learning outcomes of the material that has been studied.
5. Closing the meeting.

CONCLUSION

Based on the entire series of learning activities that have been carried out using the Jigsaw cooperative learning model, it can be concluded that the application of this model is able to increase the involvement and reading comprehension of junior high school students. Students not only understand a particular text topic more deeply, but also practice collaboration skills and the ability to teach their friends. That way, their understanding becomes more holistic and complementary. This entire process also helps them develop their communication skills and comprehensive understanding of English.

REFERENCE

- Anitra, R. (2021). Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Jigsaw dalam Pembelajaran Matematika di Sekolah Dasar. *JPDI (Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Indonesia)*, 6(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.26737/jpdi.v6i1.2311>
- BSNP. (2007). *Badan Standar Nasional Pendidikan Depdiknas*.
- Dinar, R., Sunarmo, & Wety, Y. (2021). Peningkatan Kemampuan Pemahaman Membaca Melalui Teknik Jigsaw. *Jurnal.Stkipkusumanegara.Ac.Id*, 219–223. <http://jurnal.stkipkusumanegara.ac.id/index.php/semnara2020/article/view/1188>
- Faridatuunnisa, I. (2020). Kebijakan dan Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Bahasa Inggris untuk SD di Indonesia. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional*, 191–199. <https://jurnal.ustjogja.ac.id/index.php/semnas2020/article/view/7510/3475>
- Lubis, N. A., & Harahap, H. (2016). Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Jigsaw | Jurnal As-Salam. *Jurnal Assalam*, 1(1), 96–102. <https://jurnal-assalam.org/index.php/JAS/article/view/48>
- Maro, R. K. (1981). Strategi Pembelajaran K-13 Melatih Critical Thinking. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 53(9), 1689–1699.
- Mumpuni, A., & Afifah, N. (2022). Buletin Ilmiah Pendidikan ANALISIS PEMBELAJARAN MEMBACA DAN MENULIS PERMULAAN SISWA KELAS II SEKOLAH DASAR. *Buletin Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 1(2), 73–80.
- Nuraeni, dkk. (2019). Meningkatkan Pemahaman Membaca Siswa melalui Teknik Jigsaw. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pendidikan STKIP Kusuma Negara*, 1982, 1–6. <http://jurnal.stkipkusumanegara.ac.id/index.php/semnara2019/article/view/328>
- Rofii, M. A. (2022). Model Jig saw Di Pembelajaran PJOK Kelas 6 Materi Alat Kebersihan Reproduksi. *Kalam Cendekia: Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan*, 10(2), 287. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jkc.v10i2.65630>
- Muhaenah. (2023). Penerapan perangkat pembelajaran kooperatif tipe Jigsaw untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar Bahasa Inggris siswa kelas VII-1 SMP Negeri 1 Mallusetasi. *Jurnal Edukasi Sainifik*, 3(1), 1–12.
- Suharti. (2017). Cooperative learning model jigsaw sebagai upaya meningkatkan kemampuan memahami teks narrative siswa kelas VIII A SMPN 28 Purworejo semester 2 tahun

2016/2017 (Tesis Magister). *Program Studi Magister Manajemen, STIE Widya Wiwaha, Yogyakarta.*

Arends, R. (1997). *Instructional dan Manajemen kelas. New York: Mc Graw Company.*

Laboro, Pertiwi. Peningkatan Hasil Membaca Pemahaman melalui Strategi Pembelajaran Kooperatif (Suatu Penelitian Tindakan di Kelas V Sekolah Dasar Negeri Nomor 90 Kota Gorontalo). *Tesis. Jakarta: Universitas Negeri Jakarta. (2010).*

Isjoni. (2009). Pembelajaran Kooperatif Meningkatkan Kecerdasan Komunikasi Antar Peserta Didik: *Pustaka Pelajar. Jakarta.*

Lie A, Cooperative Learning (2004). *Mempraktikkan Cooperative Learning di Ruang Kelas, Jakarta: Grasindo.*

Sharan, Shlomo (2012). *Handbook of Cooperative Learning, terjemahan Sigit Prawoto. Yogyakarta: Familia.*

Tri Astutik, Desy and Kuntarto, Eko and Hayati, Suci (2021) Analisis Kesulitan Membaca Permulaan Siswa Kelas II Sekolah Dasar. *S1 thesis, Universitas Jambi.*